

Poster-E01: Synergistic Microplastic Degradation In Wastewater: How Can Electrochemical Oxidation Enhance Biodegradation?

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Microplastics (MPs) accumulation is a pervasive environmental issue that poses risks to human health, wildlife, and ecosystems. WWTP effluent is a major pathway for MPs to infiltrate ecosystems, contributing 37% of MPs entering the world's oceans¹, despite the ability of WWTPs to remove a substantial fraction of these particles. Removal strategies in WWTPs rely in physical separation of MPs into sludge rather than their degradation, which is problematic since sludge can be used as a fertilizer.

This study presents a bioelectrochemical platform targeting the degradation of polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP), two widely used thermoplastic polymers known for their high resistance to biodegradation. The platform currently consists of two separate steps: an Electro-Fenton process to pre-oxidize plastics, enhancing biodegradability by modifying their surface²; followed by a bioreactor for their biodegradation. First, Electro-Fenton is performed in a single-cell reactor with a stainless-steel cathode and titanium metal mixed oxide anode, operating at 0.5 A for 5 hours with an iron concentration of 10 mg/L. Changes in the biodegradability of plastic samples were subsequently tested using an aerobic enriched culture for PE and PP degraders. Plastic modification and degradation were assessed through weight loss, particle distribution, and FT-IR, while biodegradability was evaluated by monitoring oxygen consumption with plastic as the sole carbon source over 21 days.

Tests were performed with granular pure PE (200–500 µm) and naturally weathered plastics from an agricultural site (PE and PP, 1 cm² pieces). None of the plastics tested showed significant weight loss after 5 hours of Electro-Fenton treatment and in 21 days of biological degradation. However, in granular pure PE, particle distribution analysis showed disaggregation into smaller particles. Similarly, FT-IR analysis revealed that Electro-Fenton induced significant structural changes and introduced functional groups (e.g., ester, ketone, acid, vinyl) in the polymer structure in tested plastics. Biodegradation tests (BOD measurements in 21 days, Figure 1) suggested Electro-Fenton pretreatment enhanced plastic biodegradability, increasing the BOD threefold the in pure PE, twofold in real PE, and fourfold in real PP. Our findings suggest Electro-Fenton can be a promising methodology to enhance plastic biodegradability by accelerating the weathering of highly recalcitrant polymers.

Figure 1: (Left) Summary of the overall treatment. (Right) Main results of plastic biodegradation without pretreatment (gray bar) and after electro-Fenton (EF) pretreatment (yellow bar).

References:

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